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Research Article

**FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF HERBAL BODY
LOTION**Shiva Ramkisan Dhande^{1*}, Puja Bekatet², Swati P. Deshmukh³^{1*}Department of Pharmacy, Shraddha Institute of Pharmacy, Washim, Maharashtra, India.²Department of Pharmacy, Shraddha Institute of Pharmacy, Washim, Maharashtra, India.³Department of Pharmacology, Shraddha Institute of Pharmacy, Washim, Maharashtra, India.**Abstract:**

The present study focuses on the formulation and evaluation of a herbal body lotion using natural ingredients known for their beneficial effects on the skin. The objective was to develop a safe, effective, and skin-friendly topical preparation incorporating herbal extracts such as aloe vera, and turmeric. These herbs were selected for their antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, moisturizing, and antioxidant properties. The lotion base was prepared using standard emulsifying agents, humectants, emollients, and preservatives, ensuring stability and skin compatibility.

Various formulations were developed and evaluated for physical parameters including pH, viscosity, spreadability, homogeneity, and stability under different storage conditions. The final optimized formulation showed desirable characteristics, with a pH value compatible with human skin (5.5–6.5), smooth texture, good spreadability, and excellent stability without phase separation. Microbial limit tests confirmed the absence of pathogenic organisms, ensuring the product's safety. Additionally, a skin irritation test was conducted on volunteers, showing no adverse effects.

The study concludes that herbal body lotion formulated with natural plant extracts can serve as an effective alternative to synthetic cosmetic products, offering therapeutic benefits while minimizing side effects. Further studies may focus on long-term stability and extended dermatological testing to validate its commercial potential.

KEYWORDS: formulation, evaluation, herbal body lotion, Indian Jujube, Aloe vera gel, Turmeric etc.

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INTRODUCTION:

The word „Cosmetic“ derived from a Greek word – „kosmesticos“ that means to Adorn. From that time any Materials used to Beautification or promoting appearance Is known As cosmetic. The word “cosmetics” Actually stems from its use in Ancient Rome. They were typically produced by female slaves known as “cosmetic” Which Is where the word “cosmetics” stemmed from. Cosmetics are used to enhance appearance. Makeup has been around for many centuries. [1] The First known people who used cosmetics to Enhance their Beauty were the Egyptians. Makeup Those days was just simple eye coloring or some Material for the body. Now-a-days makeup plays An important role for both men and women. The Importance of cosmetics has increased as many People want to stay young and attractive. Cosmetics are readily available today in the form of creams, lipstick, perfumes, eyeshadows, nail Polishes, hair sprays etc. Other cosmetics like face powder Give glow to the skin after applying the base cream. Then we have lipsticks, which are applied by many women of all ages. They are made from wax and cocoa butter in the desired amount. Cosmetics like creams, gels, and colognes are used on a daily basis by both women and men. Creams act as a Cleanser for the face in many circumstances. More recently anti- ageing creams have been manufactured which can retain younger looking skin for many years. The best cleansing agents are cleansing cream, soap and Water. Cosmetic creams serve as a skin food for Hard, dry and chapped skin. It mainly lubricates, Softens and Removes unwanted dirt from the Skin. Some popular fat creams that are used Include Vaseline and Lanolin. Dry creams are used In the manufacture of soap and gelatin which is Used as a base for the skin. Herbal Cosmetics, here Referred as Products, are formulated, using various Permissible cosmetic ingredients to form the base In which one or more herbal ingredients are used to Provide defined cosmetic advantages only, shall be Called as “Herbal Cosmetics”. The herbal cosmetics Are those when natural herbs and their products Used for their aromatic value in cosmetic Preparation among consumers for herbal products .triggered the demand for natural products and Natural extracts in cosmetics preparations. Lotions Are liquid preparations meant for external Application without friction. They are applied Directly to skin with the help of some absorbent Material, such as, cotton wool or gauze soaked in it. Lotions may be used for local action as cooling, Soothing or protective purposes. Herbal Lotion, Hererz referred as Products, are formulated, using Various permissible cosmetic ingredients To Form The base in which one or more herbal ingredients Are used to provide Defined

cosmetic advantages Only, Shall be called as “Herbal Cosmetics”. The Herbal lotion are those when natural herbs and Their products Used For their Aromatic value in Cosmetic preparation among consumers for Herbal products Triggered the Demand For natural Products and natural extracts in cosmetics Preparations. Lotions are liquid preparations that Is for External application without Friction. They Are applied directly to skin it the help of some Absorbent material, Such as, cotton wool or gauze Soaked in it. .

PLANT AND DRUG PROFILE

1. Coconut oil

- **Family:** Arecaceae
- **Synonyms:** Cocos oil, Coconut butter, Nariyal ka tel
- **Biological Source:** Dried kernel (copra) of *Cocos nucifera*
- **Chemical Constituents:**

Lauric acid (major)

Myristic, Palmitic, Caprylic, Capric

Fig.No.1: Coconut Oil

acids, Oleic, Linoleic acids, Vitamin E, K.

2. Alovera gel

- **Family:** Asphodelaceae (formerly Liliaceae)
- **Synonyms:** Ghritkumari, Aloe, Kumari
- **Biological Source:** Dried juice of the leaves of *Aloe barbadensis* (also Aloe vera)
- **Chemical Constituents:** Anthraquinones (Aloin, Aloe-emodin) Polysaccharides (Acemannan). Enzymes,

Fig.No. 2: Alovera Gel

Vitamins (A, C, E, B12), Amino acids, Minerals

3. BEESWAX

- **Family:** Apidae
- **Synonyms:** Cera flava (yellow beeswax)
- **Biological Source:** Purified wax obtained from the honeycomb of *Apis mellifera* (honey bee)
- **Chemical Constituents:**

Fig.No. 3: Beeswax

Myricyl palmitate, Cerotic acid, Hydrocarbons, Esters of fatty acids and alcohol.

4. Borax

- **Family:** Borate mineral
- **Synonyms:** Sodium borate, Tincal, Disodium tetraborate
- **Biological Source:** Naturally mined mineral from boron-rich deposits
- **4. Chemical:** $\text{Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$ – white

Fig.No. 4 : Borax

crystalline, water-soluble salt of boron

5. Rose water

- **Family:** Borate mineral
- **Synonyms:** Sodium borate, Tincal, Disodium tetraborate
- **Biological Source:** Naturally mined mineral from boron-rich deposits
- **Chemical:** $\text{Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$ – white crystalline, water-soluble salt of boron

Fig. No. 5: Rose Water

PLAN OF WORK

➤ STEP 1: Literature Review

- Study herbal ingredients by exfoliating, cleansing, and skin-rejuvenating properties.
- Review previous research on herbal facial scrubs.
- Understand regulatory guidelines for herbal cosmetic formulations [16].

➤ STEP 2: Selection of Herbal Ingredients

- Choose ingredients based on their functions:
 - Exfoliants (e.g., Indian jujube)
 - Cleansers (e.g., Aloe Vera gel)
 - Antioxidants. (e.g., Turmeric,)
 - Humectants & Soothing Agents. (e.g., aloe vera, honey) [17].

- **STEP 3: Formulation Development**
 - Prepare different formulations by varying ingredient concentrations.
 - Optimize the formulation based on texture, spreadability, and skin compatibility.
 - Evaluation Parameters [18].
- **STEP 4: Physicochemical Evaluation**
 - PH measurement (skin-friendly, 4.5–6.5).
 - Spreadability test (ease of application)
 - Viscosity measurement (consistency analysis).
 - Particle size analysis (exfoliate granule size) [19].
- **STEP 5: Stability Studies**
 - Accelerated stability testing (temperature & humidity variations).
 - Freeze-thaw stability.
 - Phase separation & microbial growth analysis [20].
- **STEP 6: Performance Evaluation**
 - Foamability test (if foaming ingredients are present).
 - Washing efficiency test (dirt & oil removal).
 - Moisturization & skin irritation tests (on volunteers or synthetic skin models) [21].
- **STEP 7: Safety & Efficacy Study**
 - Patch testing for skin irritation.
 - Consumer perception studies (volunteer-based) [22].
- **STEP 8: Documentation & Regulatory Compliance**
 - Follow guidelines from regulatory bodies (FDA, AYUSH, or other local authorities)

- Labeling and claim substantiation [23].
- **STEP 9: Conclusion & Report Writing**
 - Summarize findings.
 - Compare with existing market products.
 - Suggest future improvements [24].

MATERIAL

Table No.1: Material

Sr. No.	Ingredients	Role Of Ingredients
1.	Beeswax	Stiffening agent in cosmetic.
2.	Coconut Oil	Moisturizer,antiseptic effect.
3.	Alovera Gel	Anti-inflammatory.
4.	Borax	Antiseptic,anti-inflammatory.
5.	Rose water	Vehicle.

METHOD'S AND EVALUATION

- **Methodology**
 - Dissolve borax in rose water at 70°C on a Water bath
 - Melt the wax with coconut oil in another Beaker on water bath
 - keep the temperature at about 70°C Pour borax Solution into molten wax at the same Temperature with constant stirring
 - Stirr the mass constantly when the temperature Drops to about 45°C Pour the formulation in wide mouth container And lable it.[23,24]
- ❖ **Formulation table**

Table No. 2: Formulation table

1.Beeswax	5g	6g	5g
2.Coconut Oil	4ml	4ml	3ml
3.Alovera Gel	3g	3g	4g
4.Borax	3g	3g	5g
5.Rose Water	5ml	4ml	3ml

EVALUATION PARAMETERS

- **Organoleptic character**
 - Colour – White
 - Odour -Pleasant
 - Texture –Smooth
 - State – Semi-solid
- **Physical character:-**
 - Homogenicity.

Fig. No. 6:Herbal lotion

- PH determination, Determination of spreadability, Irritancy test, Washability.
- **Homogeneity :** The formulation were tested for homogeneity by Visual appearance and by touch.
- **PH determination:** 0.5 g cream was taken and dispersed in 50 ML distilled water and then PH was measured by Using digital PH meter.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

1. PH Determination

Sr.No	Formulation	PH
1.	F1	6.5
2.	F2	6.9
3.	F3	7.1

Table No. 3

2. Determination of Spreadability

Sr.No	Formulation	Time	Sprediability(gm×cm/sec)
1	F1	8	32.6
2.	F2	11	22.8
3.	F3	14	15

Table No. 4

3. Irritation test

Table No. 5

Sr.No	Formulation	Irritancy	Erythema,	Edema
1.	F1	Nil	Nil	Nil
2.	F2	Nil	Nil	Nil
3.	F3	Nil	Nil	Nil

4. Washability Test :-

Sr.No	Formulation	Washability
1.	F1	Easy Washable
2.	F2	Easy Washable
3.	F3	Easy Washable

Table No.6

- **Determination of Spreadability :** Sample was applied between two glass slides And was compressed to uniform thickness by Placing 100gm weight for 5 minutes. Weight was Added to the pan. The time required to separate the Two slides, i.e. the time in which the upper glass Slide moved over the lower slide was taken as Measure of Spreadability. It was Calculated using

The formula : Spreadability= $m \cdot I / t$

m-Weight tide to upper slide ,l – Length moved on the glass slide , t-time

- **Irritancy test:** Mark the area (2 cm²) on the left-hand Dorsal surface. Then the cream was applied to that Area and the time was noted. Then it is checked For irritancy, erythema, and edema any for an Interval up to 24 h and reported.
- **Washability:** A portion of lotion was applied over the Skin of hand and allowed to flow under the Force of flowing tap water for 10 minutes. The time When the lotion completely removed was noted.

Discussion

- The present research was the formulation And evaluation of herbal body lotion. The evaluation Parameters were coming under results, like the Physical evaluation of herbal body lotion, PH of the lotion, Spreadability, Washability, non-irritancy Test, of the herbal pain relieving Lotion was shown in table 3,4,5,6
- All the three formulations F1 ,F2 , and F3 Showed good appearance, PH, Determination of Spredability. Also, the Formulations F1, F2, and F3 Showed no redness, Erythema and irritation during Irritancy study and They were easily washable.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

Summary:

The present work focus on the potential Of herbal extracts from cosmetic purposes. The Uses of cosmetic have been increased in many Folds in personal care system. The Use of bioactive Ingredient in cosmetic influence biological Functions of skins and Provide nutrients necessary For the healthy skin. There are numerous herbs Available naturally having different uses in Cosmetic preparations for skincare as Antioxidants. The present study revealed that Herbal cosmetic are very safe and does not Produce any toxic and adverse reactions compare To marketed cosmetics products. Herbal Lotion we Will avoid skin problems. By using Aloe Vera gel, Coconut oil and Rose water the Lotion showed a multipurpose effect and all these herbal Ingredients showed significant different activities. Based on results and discussion, the formulations F1, F2 and F3 were stable at room temperature and can be safely used on the skin.

CONCLUSION:

The formulated herbal body lotion demonstrated desirable physicochemical properties, including appropriate pH, smooth texture, good spreadability, and acceptable viscosity. The use of natural ingredients such as aloe vera, neem, turmeric, and essential oils contributed to its moisturizing, antimicrobial, and soothing effects. Evaluation results confirmed the stability and safety of the formulation over the test period. Overall, the herbal body lotion offers a promising alternative to synthetic products, aligning with the growing demand for natural and skin-friendly cosmetic preparations.

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